

Impact of Root Zone Temperature (RZT) on Nutrient Uptake of Crops

¹S. Sivagnanam, ²Jagadeeswaran. R and ²V. P. Duraisami

¹School of Agriculture, Bharath Institute of Higher Education and Research, Selaiyur, Chennai – 600 073.

²Natural Resource Management, Tamil Nadu Agricultural University, Coimbatore.

Growth and development of a plant are influenced mainly by solar radiation, temperature, soil moisture, soil aeration and mineral nutrients. In addition, other factors also influence crop growth at different stages. Stress is any change in environmental conditions that might reduce or adversely change plant's growth and development and biological strain is the reduced or changed function of the plants in response to stress (Levitt, 1980). The plant growths are affected by two different types of stress biotic (living organisms) and abiotic (temperature, water, chemicals, radiation, wind, sound, magnetic, electrical etc.). A major challenge of successful crop management today is coping with oxidative stress associated with plant abiotic and biotic stresses (Harsco Corporation, 2013).

Soil temperature is one of the primary factors affecting plant growth (pregitzer and King, 2005). Soil temperature affects plant growth, nutrient/water uptake, Organic matter decomposition etc. Different authors have reported improved growth and photosynthesis rate by raising soil RZT (Day *et al.*, 1991; Landhausser *et al.*, 1996 and Schwarz *et al.*, 1997). The role of RZT on plant growth is to control the root zone layer more directly. There is evidence that nutrient / water uptake is affected by nutrient solution temperature (Borowski, 1995). The relative translocation of nutrients from roots to shoots seemed to be controlled by Root Zone Temperature (Mozafar *et al.*, 1993). Temperature directly and indirectly regulates DOM (decomposition of organic matter) production through its influence on biological activities and physico-chemical processes (Stutter, 2007). Increases RZT and reduced allocation of N supply to roots and leaves, and increased allocation to stem, although an effect on carbon assimilation rate was not observed (Gavito *et al.*, 2001). In a study of *Lactuca sativa* L. cv. (baby butter fruit) Palma under aeroponical conditions, Tan *et al.*, (2002) found that plants grow at optimum cool RZT had higher leaf P concentration compared to the plants grown at hot A-RZT.

Tomato (*Solanum lycopersicum* L.) plant growing at 36°C RZT for 20 d exhibited decreased shoot growth and P uptake compare with plants growing at 25°C RZT (Klock *et al.*, 1997). Chilling decreases root hydraulic conductance and slows down water absorption on the one hand, and on the other hand, impairs stomatal control which leads to excessive water loss and leaf wilting (Capell and Dorffling, 1993; Bloom *et al.*, 2004).

What is soil temperature and root zone temperature?

The ideal plant growth temperature is 4.5°C to 35°C. Plant needs different temperature for different stages of growth likewise, seed germination (10 – 30°C), optimum root growth temperature (20-25°C) and optimum microorganism growth (25-35°C) and some plants tolerate to develop under high and low temperature less than 4°C and more than 35°C.

The main source of soil temperature is sunlight. The heat energy transfer in to the soil in three basic process **convection, conduction and radiation**. The flow of heat as a result of mixing or turbulence (heat flow liquid or gasses) known as convection. Heat flow through a body by the transference of the momentum of individual molecules without mixing, the process is known as molecular conduction or simply conduction (flow of heat tack place: one molecule to another). The process of transference of heat energy through space by means of electromagnetic waves called radiation (black body absorbs most of the radiation than body).

Important Soil Temperature Cycle

Diurnal cycle, during day time soil gets heated and expressed maximum in after noon and minimum during morning. The soil is a poor conductor of heat and therefore this cycle is effective up to **30cm depth**. Annual cycle, soil temperatures during the whole year include summer and winter seasons. This cycle is operative upto **15-20 meters depth** and Seasonal cycle, manifests variation of soil temperature for any **particular season** (growing).

Mathematical thermal conductivity

Heat flow in steady-state condition has been reached; it is found that the quantity of heat flowing per unit area in unit time is proportional to the difference in temperature across the distance Δx . Mathematically, it is written, **Fourier's law of heat conduction**

$$qh = \frac{dy}{dx} \lambda$$

where q'_h – quantity of heat passing per unit time through the soil slab from x_1 to x_2 , $\text{cal cm}^{-2} \text{sec}^{-1}$; λ = proportionality constant, known as thermal conductivity of the slab in the direction of heat flow, $\text{cal cm}^{-1} \text{sec}^{-1} \text{ } ^\circ\text{C}$. dT/dx temperature gradient, $^\circ\text{C cm}^{-1}$.

Fig. 1. A conceptual diagram depicting relationships between plant and soil factors that control the availability and uptake of mineral nutrients.

Soil temperature affects nutrient uptake directly by altering root growth, morphology, and uptake kinetics. Indirect effects include altered rates of decomposition and nutrient mineralization, mineral weathering, and nutrient transport processes (mass flow and diffusion). (Modified from Fig. 1 in Bassiri Rad 2000).

Functions of roots

The functions of roots include anchorage, the absorption of water and mineral nutrients, synthesis of various essential compounds such as growth regulators, and the storage of food in root crops. Plants require a balanced supply of nutrients throughout their development. Generally, they have accumulated most of their nutrients by sometime between the flowering and ripening stages to fill developing fruit or seed.

Fig.2. This diagram illustrates the path of water and inorganic materials as they move into, through, and out of the plant body.

Water potential in a plant regulates movement of water. At the roots there is positive water potential (except in the case of severe drought). On the surface of leaves and other organs, water loss called **transpiration** creates a negative pressure. It depends on its osmotic absorption by the roots and the negative pressures created by water loss from the leaves and other plant surfaces (fig.2). The negative pressure generated by transpiration is largely responsible for the upward movement of water in xylem.

Most of the water absorbed by the plant comes in through root hairs, which collectively have an enormous surface area (fig. 2). Root hairs are almost always turgid because their solute potential is greater than that of the surrounding soil due to mineral ions being actively pumped into the cells. Because the mineral ion concentration in the soil water is usually much lower than it is in the plant, an expenditure of energy (supplied by ATP) is required for the accumulation of such ions in root cells. The plasma membranes of root hair cells contain a variety of protein transport channels, through which *proton pumps* transport specific ions against even large concentration gradients. Once in the roots, the ions, which are plant nutrients, are transported via the xylem throughout the plant.

The ions may follow the cell walls and the spaces between them or more often go directly through the plasma membranes and the protoplasm of adjacent cells. When mineral ions pass between the cell walls, they do so non-selectively. Eventually, on their journey inward, they reach the endodermis and any further passage through the cell walls is blocked by the Casparian strips. Water and ions must pass through the plasma membranes and protoplasts of the endodermal cells to reach the xylem. However, transport through the cells of the endodermis is selective. The endodermis, with its unique structure, along with the cortex and epidermis, controls which ions reach the xylem.

Nutrient Mobility in Soil and Plants Mechanisms

Ion absorption by plant roots requires contact between the ion and the root surface. There are generally three ways in which nutrient reach the root surface: (1) Root interception, (2) mass flow and (3) diffusion. The relative importance of these mechanisms in supplying nutrients to plant root is shown in table 1 and 2.

Table. 1. Primary uptake mechanism of nutrient to roots

Nutrient	Root Interception	Mass flow	Diffusion
N		✓	
P	✓		✓
K			✓
Ca		✓	

Mg		✓	
S		✓	
Mn			✓
Zn			✓
Fe	✓		✓
Cu	✓		
B		✓	

1. Root interception represents, the root can pump into the ion (physical contact between root and mineral surfaces) as it grows through the soil.
2. Mass flow, the soluble fraction of nutrients which are present in solution (water) and are not held on the soil fractions flow to the root as water is taken up. It is reduced at low temperatures because the transpiration demands of plants and water evaporation at the soil surface decreases at low soil temperatures.
3. Diffusion occurs when an ion moves from an area of high concentration to one of low concentration. As roots absorb nutrients from the surrounding soil solution.

Mass flow and diffusion processes are also important in nutrient management. Soils that exhibit low diffusion rates because of high BC, low soil moisture or high clay content may require application of immobile nutrients near the roots to maximize nutrient availability and plant uptake.

Table. 2. Significance of Root interception, Mass Flow and Diffusion in ion transport to crop roots

Nutrients	Percent nutrient up take by corn crop		
	Root interception	Mass Flow	Diffusion
Nitrogen	<1	80	19
Phosphorus	2	5	93
Potassium	2	18	80
Calcium	150	375	0
Magnesium	33	600	0
Sulphur	5	300	0

(Dave Mengel, 1995).

Ion Absorption by Plants

Plants uptake of ions from the soil solution can be described by *passive and active processes*, where ions passively move to a “boundary” through which ions are actively

transported to organ in plant cells that metabolize the nutrient ions. Solution composition or ion concentrations outside and inside of the boundary are controlled by different processes, each essential to plant nutrition and growth.

A molecule or ion is transported actively or passively across a membrane (caseparian band, plasma membrane or tonoplast) depends on the concentration and charge of the ion, or molecule, which in combination represent the electrochemical driving force. Ion and molecules diffuse from areas of high to low concentrations. Thus diffusion does not require the plant to expend energy. In contrast, for ions diffusing against the concentration gradient, energy is required. Thus, passive transport across the plasma membrane for example, occurs with the electrochemical potential and active transport occurs against the electrochemical potential, a process that required the cell expend energy.

Table. 3. Rooting depth of various crops

Shallow-rooted (0 - 60 cm)	Medium-rooted (60 - 90 cm)	Deep-rooted (90 - 120 cm)	Very deep-rooted (>180 cm)
Rice	Groundnut	Cotton	Citrus
Onion	Castor	Maize	Grapevine
Cabbage	Tobacco	Sorghum	Safflower
Cauliflower	Wheat	Sugarcane	Coffee
Potato	Chillies'	Pearl millet	Lucerne
lettuce	French bean	Tomato	
	carrots	soybean	

Different Types of Thermometers

1. Electrical Thermometers
2. **Liquid-in-glass Thermometers**
 - a. **Soil thermometers (Bent-stem soil thermometer)**
3. Bimetallic Thermographs
4. Clock-driven Drums
5. Louvered Screens
6. Ventilated Shields

Soil Thermometer (Bent-stem soil thermometer)

Fig. 3. Soil thermometers (Bent-stem soil thermometer)

This thermometer measures the soil temperature. It measures soil temperature of shallow layer, mercury-in-glass thermometer with its stem bent at right angle or any other suitable angle below the lowest graduation. The thermometer bulb is sunk into the ground to the required depth, generally 5, 10, 15 and 20cm.

Sensors for Measuring Soil Heat Flux

The HFP01 Soil Heat Flux Plate uses a thermopile to measure temperature gradients across its plate. Operating in a completely passive way, it generates a small output voltage that is proportional to this differential temperature. Assuming that the heat flux is steady, that the thermal conductivity of the body is constant, and that the sensor has negligible influence on the thermal flow pattern, the signal of the HFP01 is directly proportional to the local heat flux. The HFP01's

output is in millivolts. To convert this measured voltage to heat flux, it must be divided by the plate's calibration constant. A unique calibration constant is supplied with each sensor.

Fig.4. Soil Heat Flux Plate uses a thermopile to measure temperature

Placement in Soil

The standard set of sensors for measuring soil heat flux includes two HF01 Soil Heat Flux Plates, one TCAV Averaging Soil Thermocouple, and one CS616, CS650, or CS655 water content reflectometer. These sensors are installed as shown in (Figure 4). The location of the heat flux plates and thermocouple should be chosen to be representative of the area under study. If the ground cover is extremely varied, an additional set of sensors is required to provide a valid soil heat flux average. Use a small shovel to make a vertical slice in the soil. Excavate the soil to one side of the slice. Keep this soil intact so that it can be replaced with minimal disruption. The sensors are installed in the undisturbed face of the hole. Measure the sensor depths from the top of the hole. With a small knife, make a horizontal cut 8 cm below the surface into the undisturbed face of the hole. Insert the heat flux plate into the horizontal cut. Not: Install the HFP01 in the soil such that the side with the red label is facing the sky and the side with a blue label facing the soil.

CAUTION: In order for the HFP01 to make quality soil heat flux measurements, the plate must be in full contact with the soil. Never run the sensor leads directly to the surface. Rather, bury the sensor leads a short distance back from the hole to minimize thermal conduction on the lead wire. Replace the excavated soil back into its original position after all the sensors are installed. Note: To protect sensor cables from damage caused by rodents, it is recommended to bury them inside of flexible electrical tubing.

RZT with nutrient interaction & growth

The role of RZT on plant growth is to control the root zone layer more directly. There is evidence that nutrient / water uptake is affected by nutrient solution temperature by (Borowski, 1995). Mozafar *et al.*, (1993) have reported that relative translocation of nutrients from roots to shoots seemed to be controlled by Root Zone Temperature. Maize grown at low root temperatures (12 -18⁰C) not only declined in root growth but also in aerial growth in comparison with values for high temperatures 24⁰C (Engels and Marschner, 1996).

RZT with decomposition of Organic matter, nitrogen and carbon

Temperature directly and indirectly regulates DOM production through its influence on biological activities and physico-chemical processes (Stutter, 2007). Increases in RZT and reduced allocation of N supply to roots and leaves and increased allocation to stem,

although an effect on carbon assimilation rate was not observed (Gavito *et al.*, 2001).

Influence of Temperature on DOC, HI and Nitrate

The study site was located within a long-term research watershed operation by the USDA in Pennsylvania, USA (Bryant, 2011). In 2009, we installed tension and zero-tension lysimeter at 20(A horizon), 40 and 60 cm (B horizon) depth in a mixed oak-hickory forest that had not been harvested for >50 years. The soil is categorized as Typic Dystrudept. Lysimeters were installed along with one moisture-temperature sensor at each depth (Decagon Devices, USA).

Fig. 5. Regression coefficients between dissolved organic carbon (DOC), humification index (HI) and soil

solution nitrate with soil temperature. * and ** indicate P values ≤ 0.05 and ≤ 0.01 , respectively.

Soil temperature was positively associated with DOC concentration ($R^2 = 0.23-0.77$, $P \leq 0.05$) and complexity (HI) of DOM ($R^2 = 0.35-0.72$, $P \leq 0.05$) for both lysimeter types (Fig.5). Although soil temperature was positively correlated with nitrate sampled from zero-tension lysimeters at 20 cm, it was negatively correlated with nitrate sampled from the tension lysimeters at 40 cm and both lysimeter types at 60 cm. The regression coefficients among these variables were i) higher for DOM sampled from tension lysimeters and ii) increased with soil depth for HI (Fig. 5).

Under favorable conditions, increasing soil temperature (10°C -30°C) enhances microbial activity, resulting in accelerated SOM solubilization that is subsequently assimilated or mineralized (Bengtson and Bengtsson 2007, Borken, and Matzner, 2009, Swift, 1979). However, the energy budget theory of microbially driven SOM

depolymerization suggests that the consistently larger DOM pool at greater soil temperatures (Fig. 5).

Interaction effects on Constant Shoot and Different RZT Treatments on Wheat

Root Zone Temperature Experiments: A replicated, 28-d-long experiment consisting of growing vegetative wheat crops in elevated RZTs [$+0^{\circ}\text{C}$ (24°C), $+4^{\circ}\text{C}$ (28°C), $+6^{\circ}\text{C}$ (30°C), $+8^{\circ}\text{C}$ (32°C), and $+11^{\circ}\text{C}$ (35°C)], while keeping air temperature constant (24°C), was conducted. The PESTO experiment used 21-d-old plants, but here the experiment was extended to 28 DAP to allow changes in partitioning in response to RZT to be observed. A control of 24°C RZT was used because RZT during the PESTO ground tests equaled the

24°C air temperature.

Fig. 6. Effects of shoot (T_{SHOOT}) and root zone (T_{ROOT}) temperature on plant height during

development of wheat. Observations represent means \pm standard error.

Fig. 7. Effects of shoot (T_{SHOOT}) and root zone (T_{ROOT}) temperature treatments on total leaf area during development of wheat. Observations represent means \pm standard error.

Growth at elevated RZT did not alter the leaf appearance rates because all plants from all treatments reached the same Haun stage of 3.5 by 15 DAP. A $+4^{\circ}\text{C}$ (28°C RZT) increase in RZT above-air temperature (Fig. 6) did not affect plant height until after 15 DAP (or 10 d after the RZT treatments began). Significant differences in plant height were evident by 15 DAP for RZTs greater than $+6^{\circ}\text{C}$ (30°C RZT) above air temperature. The plants growing at 35°C RZT were severely stunted and eventually died by 22 DAP.

Leaf area was more sensitive to elevated RZT than plant height (Fig. 7). Leaf area was reduced after exposure to 10 d of RZTs exceeding $+4^{\circ}\text{C}$ (28°C RZT) above air temperature and after 2 d of exposure at the $+11^{\circ}\text{C}$ (35°C RZT) treatment. Leaf area expansion had decreased significantly by 22 DAP for RZTs greater than $+4^{\circ}\text{C}$ above the control (24°C air temperature and 24°C RZT). Although morphologic changes were observed when RZT is increased by up to $+6^{\circ}\text{C}$, there were no effects observed on physiological processes like leaf photosynthesis or g_s . However, at very high RZTs ($+11^{\circ}\text{C}$ above air temperature), photosynthesis and g_s was severely hampered, and the plants died after 16 d (Oscar Monje, 2007).

Effect of RZT on different nutrient treatments in cucumber seedlings

Root-zone temperatures (RZT) (12°C -RZT and 20°C -RZT) and different N, P, and K nutrient regimes on the growth, reactive oxygen species (ROS), and antioxidant enzyme in cucumber seedlings were investigated in hydroponics. The temperature control equipment consisted of a polyvinyl chloride box, plastic pots, sand, and heating wires. The internal dimensions of the polyvinyl chloride box were 240 cm long, 70 cm wide and 20 cm deep. Each box contained 48 pots. 8 pots for each nutrient treatment were randomly distributed in the box. The space between pots in the polyvinyl chloride box was filled with sand, in which heating wires (DV, Ningbo, China, 800 W 100 m) were imbedded. Through the heating wires, heat was delivered to sand, and then to the solutions in plastic pots. Temperature was regulated by a temperature controller and timing device (Fig. 8). Plants were grown in the box glass greenhouse under two different nutrient (Hoagland's) solution temperatures while their aerial parts were subjected to the same air temperature condition. The air and root-zone temperatures of a typical experimental day were showed in Fig. 5. The unheated nutrient solution temperature, ranged from 8°C at 18:00 to 11.9°C at 8:00 a.m. of the next day, as the treatment of $(12 \pm 2)^{\circ}\text{C}$ (12°C -RZT), and the heated solution temperature was kept at constant

(20±2)°C (20°C-RZT) during this period (heating time). The temperatures were recorded by an intelligent digital recorder (LGR-WD41, Hangzhou Logger Technology Co. Ltd., China).

Fig. 8. Cross-section diagram of automatic controlling system of root-zone temperature.

Total fresh weights at elevated root-zone temperature (20°C-RZT) were significantly higher than those at low root-zone temperature (12°C-RZT) in all nutrient treatments (data not shown). Table 4 showed the growth indexes affected by RZT and nutrients. There were significant interactions between nutrient solution and RZT for the total plant dry weights ($P=0.001$), root lengths ($P=0.001$), and leaf areas ($P=0.01$), but not for the plant heights and internode lengths (Table 4). RZT had larger effects ($P=0.001$) on plant heights and stem lengths than nutrient solution ($P=0.05$) (Table 4).

Table 4 Effects of root-zone temperature on growth indexes of cucumber seedlings in the different nutrient treatments¹.

Root-zone temperature (RZT)	Nutrient treatment	Growth indexes				
		Total plant dry weight (g/plant)	Plant height (cm)	Internode length (cm)	Root length (cm)	Leaf area (cm ²)
12°C-RZT	Control	1.37 d	8.57 e	2.14 e	16.03 f	85.17 f
	Low-N	1.24 d	8.57 e	2.14 e	14.50 g	89.71 f
	High-N	1.96 c	9.64 e	2.41 e	18.12 e	132.56 b
	Low-P	1.88 c	10.78 e	2.69 e	19.50 e	124.29 d
	High-P	1.65 cd	9.78 e	2.44 e	18.60 e	108.80 e
	Low-K	1.54 d	9.71 e	2.42 e	16.50 f	103.64 e
	High-K	1.25 d	7.85 e	1.96 f	16.04 f	99.80 ef
20°C-RZT	Control	2.08 c	21.42 bcd	4.28 abcd	35.70 b	141.24 ab
	Low-N	1.90 c	18.92 d	3.78 d	24.40 d	133.68 b
	High-N	2.41 a	24.00 ab	4.80 ab	39.15 a	147.41 ab
	Low-P	2.22 b	24.42 a	4.88 a	38.50 a	158.27 a
	High-P	1.96 c	21.07 bcd	4.21 bcd	41.01 a	121.47 d
	Low-K	1.78 cd	20.00 cd	4.00 cd	28.50 c	150.25 ab
	High-K	2.29 b	22.92 abc	4.58 abc	41.50 a	174.43 a
Analysis of variance						
Nutrient solution		**	*	*	**	**
RZT		**	**	**	**	**
Nutrient solution×RZT		**	NS	NS	**	**

¹ Mean values followed by different letters within a column indicated significant differences at $P=0.05$ based on Duncan's multiple range test. NS, *, **, ***, nonsignificant, significant at $P=0.05$, $P=0.01$, and $P=0.001$, respectively. The same as below.

Total plant dry weights increased at 20°C-RZT under each nutrient treatment compared

to those at 12°C-RZT. At 12°C-RZT, total plant dry weights increased with increasing nitrogen (N) concentration, but decreased with increasing phosphorus (P) and potassium (K) concentrations. Total plant dry weights in high-N and low-P treatments were significantly higher than those of other nutrient treatments at 12°C-RZT. Irrespective of the nutrient concentrations, plant heights, internode lengths, root lengths and leaf areas were significantly suppressed at 12°C-RZT compared with those of plants grown at 20°C-RZT (Table 4), and no significant difference was found in most nutrient treatments for each growth index at 12°C-RZT, but different effects can be observed between nutrient treatments at 20°C-RZT. At 20°C-RZT, total plant dry weights increased with increasing N and K concentration, but decreased with increasing P concentration. In addition, total plant dry weights in high-N and high-K treatments at 20°C-RZT were significantly higher than those of other treatments. Plant heights in low N and K concentrations at 20°C-RZT were lower than those in high concentration, while those in P treatment showed the reverse result. Plants grown at high-K and low-P had the greatest inter-node length. Root lengths at high-N, low-P and high-P were significantly higher than those of other treatments. Moreover, roots at 12°C-RZT were short, thick, and had fewer root hairs, while those at 20°C-RZT were relatively long, thin and strongly branched.

Fig.9. Effects of root-zone temperature on root activities (A) and relatively water content (B) of cucumber seedlings (30-d-old) in different nutrient treatments.

The low root-zone temperature (12°C-RZT), the root activities of cucumber seedlings suffered seriously and were significantly lower than those at elevated root-zone temperature (20°C-RZT) in all nutrient treatments. Root activities increased with increasing N and K nutrient concentrations, but decreased with the increase of P concentration (Fig.9-A). Leaf relative water contents at 20°C-RZT in all nutrient treatments were significantly higher than those at 12°C-RZT (Fig. 9-B). There was no significant difference between nutrient treatments at each root-zone temperature (Fig. 9-B). Yan Qiu-yan., (2013) reported that

application of N could compensate the negative effects of low root temperature on biomass formation compared to those of P and K. Finally, elevating root temperature would be a more effective method than adding nutrients concentration for plant growth in cold season.

Root Zone Temperature with Phosphorus Interaction

A study of *Lactuca sativa* L. cv. (baby butter fruit) Palma under aeroponical conditions, found that plants grow at optimum cool RZT had higher leaf P concentration compared to the plants grown at hot A-RZT (Tan *et al.*, 2002). Klock *et al.*, (1997) reported Tomato (*Solanum lycopersicum* L.) plant growing at 36°C RZT for 20 d exhibited **decreased shoot growth and P uptake** compare with plants growing at 25°C RZT.

In this study, butterhead lettuce (*Lactuca sativa* L. cv. Baby Butter) plants were grown at three root-zone temperatures (RZTs): 25°C, 30°C and ambient-RZT (A-RZT) ranging from 26°C-42°C while their shoots were maintained at hot ambient temperature ranging from 26°C- 42°C. Three phosphorus (P) concentrations: -25% P (minus P, 23.25ppm), control (31.00ppm) and +25% P (plus P, 38.75ppm) were supplied to the plants at each RZT using Netherlands Standard Nutrient Solution in modified hydroponic culturing system. Interactions between RZT and P concentrations on productivity, root morphology, maximum photosynthetic O₂ evolution (P max), P uptake and its partitioning between shoot and root were studied.

Table. 5. Mean P Concentrations (mg/g DW), Total P Content of Shoot and Root and P Shoot/Root Ratio of *L. sativa* Plants Grown at Different P Concentrations in Nutrient Solution and Different RZTs for 35 Days

		Treatment			
		Tissue	-25% P	Control P	+25% P
P concentration (mg/g DW)	25°C-RZT	Shoot	5.81 ± 0.46 ^{a*}	6.62 ± 0.58 ^a	7.86 ± 0.48 ^{a*}
		Root	5.07 ± 0.36 ^d	5.67 ± 0.40 ^d	7.07 ± 0.53 ^d
	30°C-RZT	Shoot	4.8 ± 0.37 ^b	5.76 ± 0.46 ^b	7.01 ± 0.49 ^b
		Root	4.73 ± 0.22 ^e	5.95 ± 0.28 ^e	6.83 ± 0.41 ^e
	A-RZT	Shoot	4.06 ± 0.37 ^c	4.79 ± 0.36 ^c	5.84 ± 0.49 ^c
		Root	4.42 ± 0.27 ^f	5.31 ± 0.23 ^f	5.95 ± 0.35 ^f
Total P content (mg)	25°C-RZT	Shoot	20.06 ± 2.06 ^{a*}	29.17 ± 2.61 ^a	45.86 ± 3.34 ^{a*}
		Root	3.36 ± 0.32 ^d	4.22 ± 0.18 ^d	5.94 ± 0.37 ^d
	30°C-RZT	Shoot	11.31 ± 1.14 ^b	19.43 ± 0.88 ^b	31.04 ± 1.47 ^b
		Root	2.74 ± 0.23 ^e	3.94 ± 0.28 ^b	5.12 ± 0.35 ^e
	A-RZT	Shoot	5.06 ± 0.41 ^c	9.04 ± 0.66 ^c	16.56 ± 1.07 ^c
		Root	1.83 ± 0.08 ^f	2.57 ± 0.32 ^f	4.39 ± 0.24 ^f
	25°C-RZT	shoot/root ratio	5.97 ± 0.32 ^a	6.44 ± 0.58 ^a	7.72 ± 0.38 ^a
	30°C-RZT	shoot/root ratio	4.13 ± 0.29 ^b	4.69 ± 0.4 ^b	6.06 ± 0.48 ^b
	A-RZT	shoot/root ratio	2.76 ± 0.23 ^c	3.52 ± 0.17 ^c	4.92 ± 0.28 ^c

* Indicates significant difference by comparing to the control P ($P < 0.05$) by t-test at the same RZT. Means within each P treatment followed by different letters are significantly different ($P < 0.05$) based on Fisher's LSD test, n = 5.

P Uptake and Partitioning Between Shoots and Roots

Phosphorus concentrations of shoot and root as well as its partitioning between shoot and root are summarized in Table 5. At each given RZT, P concentration of shoot and root were significantly higher in the plus P plants than in the control plants ($P < 0.05$). Meanwhile, P concentrations of shoot and root were significantly lower in the minus P plants compared to those of the control plants ($P < 0.05$). On the other hand, P concentrations of shoot and root were significantly reduced when lettuce plants were grown at hot A-RZT. At each given P concentration in nutrient solution, P concentrations of shoot and root were significantly higher in 25°C-RZT plants than in hot A-RZT plants ($P < 0.05$). Both shoot and root had the highest P concentration when lettuce plants were grown with the plus P concentration at 25°C-RZT. With the minus P concentration and A-RZT, both shoot and root tissues had the lowest P concentrations. These findings suggest that there was a decrease in P concentrations of shoot and root when lettuce plants were grown with lower P concentration in the medium at hot A-

RZT. Lettuce plants grown with plus P concentration at 25°C-RZT had significantly higher shoot and root P concentrations compared to those plants grown with the plus P concentration at A-RZT ($P < 0.05$). These results suggest that P concentrations in both the shoots and root were affected by RZT and P concentration in nutrient solution. The effect of RZT on the accumulation of shoot and root P masked the effect of P concentrations in nutrient solution.

Interaction between the plus P concentration in nutrient solution and 25°C-RZT significantly enhance Pmax, thus the highest shoot and root productivity. However, plants grown with the minus P concentration at 25°C-RZT developed the largest root system. Higher P concentration in growth medium resulted in higher P concentrations in shoots and roots with a greater portion partitioned to the shoots. Luo *et al.*, (2009) concluded uptake and transport of P to the shoot was depressed when lettuce plants were grown at hot A-RZT.

Root Zone Temperature with Potassium Interaction

Influx of K to roots and transported to xylems of *Hordeum vulgare* and *Sorghum bicolor* were both reduced significantly when RZT was higher than 35°C Bassiri Rad *et al.*, (1991). Tan *et al.*, (2002) recorded reduced uptake of K by lettuce plants when grown with low K concentration at hot RZT leads to poor root development. K concentration in nutrient solution, shoot and root fresh weight of lettuce plants grown at 25°C RZT were significantly higher than at 30°C Hong *et al.*, (2012).

Lactuca sativa L. plants were grown at three root-zone temperatures (RZTs): 25°C, 30°C and ambient-RZT (A-RZT) on aeroponic system. Three potassium (K) concentrations: - 25% K (minus K), control (standard K) and +25% K (plus K) were supplied to the plants

at each RZT using Netherlands Standard Nutrient Solution.

Fig. 10. Root potassium concentration of lettuce plants grown at different concentrations and RZTs.

Lactuca plants had the highest shoot K concentration when grown with the plus K at 25°C C-RZT but they had the lowest shoot K concentration when grown with the minus K at A-RZT. For roots, however, a different pattern was observed. Lowest root K concentration was obtained from the plus K plants at 25°C C-RZT ($P < 0.05$) while the highest root K concentration was obtained from plants grown with the plus K at A-RZT. (Hong et al., 2012) find that high productivity of lettuce grown with plus K at all RZTs is the results of high proportion of absorbed K by large root system partitioning to shoots which enhances P_{max} and alters photoassimilate partitioning. To a certain extent, plus K in nutrient solution could alleviate the detrimental effects of hot A-RZT on temperate lettuce grown in the tropics.

Root Zone Temperature Influences Nutrient Accumulation and Use in Maize

Root-zone temperature (RZT) changes with season, geographical location and global warming. Nutrient accumulation and use behaviour of two maize (*Zea mays* L.) genotypes were evaluated under low ($22.4 \pm 5^\circ\text{C}$) and high ($28.8 \pm 5^\circ\text{C}$) root-zone temperatures. In greenhouse study, hybrid maize (FHY-396) and indigenous variety (EV-7004) were sown in calcareous loam soil filled in pots.

Nutrient		High RZT		Low RZT		LSD _(0.05)
		Hybrid (FHY-396)	Variety (EV-7004)	Hybrid (FHY-396)	Variety (EV-7004)	
Shoot nutrient concentration						
P	mg g ⁻¹	2.70	3.09	2.56	2.96	0.13
K		5.12	4.86	5.71	5.64	0.38
Cu	μg g ⁻¹	12.47	12.83	9.83	9.67	0.67
Zn		21.33	19.50	17.05	15.03	1.17
Root nutrient concentration						
P	mg g ⁻¹	2.88	3.33	2.82	3.23	0.09
K		2.22	2.26	1.93	2.16	0.31
Cu	μg g ⁻¹	41.67	40.83	35.00	35.00	1.92
Zn		38.39	27.63	31.08	24.58	1.37
Ratio-to-shoot concentration ratio						
P		1.07	1.08	1.10	1.09	0.06
K		0.44	0.46	0.34	0.38	0.06
Cu		0.80	0.71	1.17	0.09	0.09
Zn		1.80	1.42	1.82	1.64	0.08

(Low and high RZT differed by 4.2°C)

Table 6. Nutrient concentrations in hybrid maize (FHY-396) and indigenous variety (EV-7004) at low and high root-zone temperatures (RZT).

Concentration of nutrients

There was a significant ($p < 0.05$) effect of RZT on concentration of various nutrients in maize genotypes (Table 6). Shoot concentrations of Cu and Zn was increased by about 30% at high RZT than at low RZT. At the higher RZT, shoot P concentration was increased by 5%, whereas, K shoot concentration was decreased at high RZT as compared to low RZT. Nevertheless, root concentration of all the estimated nutrients (including K) was increased at the higher RZT. Ions typically move across the root into the xylem by traversing several layers of plasmalemma.

Root-to-shoot concentration ratio is a reliable tool to study relative translocation of a nutrient from roots to shoots. There was a significant ($p < 0.05$) effect of RZT on translocation of K, Cu and Zn (Table 6). Translocation of both the micronutrients (Cu and Zn) increased at the higher RZT. However, K heavily accumulated in roots with a reduction of its translocation to shoots at the higher RZT. The relative translocation of nutrients from roots to shoots seemed to be controlled by RZT.

Nutrient Uptake

Uptake (contents plant⁻¹) of all the estimated nutrients (P, K, Cu and Zn) in shoots and roots of maize genotypes was significantly ($p < 0.05$) increased at high RZT compared to low RZT. There was 1.5-fold increase in P and 1.4-fold increase in K shoot uptake when plants were grown at the higher RZT. Shoot uptake of Cu and Zn was more vividly influenced. A 1.9-fold increase for Cu and 1.8-fold increase for Zn was observed at high RZT than at low RZT.

Cleve *et al.*, (1990) found that soil warming improves foliar N, P and K contents. An 83% increase in shoot Zn uptake was observed in barley with rising RZT from 10°C to 23°C (Schwartz *et al.*, 1987).

Root is the mineral nutrient uptake organ of plants, and its growth undoubtedly affects nutrient uptake and transport. Nutrient uptake in roots was also similarly affected and it was remarkably more for Cu and Zn (Table 7). Indigenous variety (EV-7004) accumulated significantly ($p < 0.05$) more shoot P than hybrid maize (FHY-396), whereas, hybrid maize (FHY-396) accumulated more root Zn concentration than indigenous variety (EV-7004).

Nutrient uptake per unit parameter of root is an excellent characteristic to estimate efficiency of roots to uptake soil nutrients (Hussain *et al.*, 2009). Root zone temperature was significantly ($p < 0.05$) affected nutrient uptake per unit root dry matter (Table 7). On an average, there was 12% increase in P, 40% increase in Cu and 31% increase in Zn uptake per unit root dry matter. Increased uptake per unit root dry matter at the higher RZT could be attributed to root morphology and function, and soil physico-chemical and biological processes that are dependent on RZT (Barber, 1995).

Fig. 11. Nutrient utilisation efficiencies (NUE) of hybrid maize (FHY-396) and indigenous variety (EV-7004) at low and high root-zone temperatures (RZT) (Low and high RZT differed by 4.2°C)

Nutrient utilization efficiency and usage index

Shoot utilisation efficiencies of all nutrients (P, K, Cu and Zn) was significantly ($p < 0.05$) increased at the higher RZT (Fig. 11). Increased nutrient utilisation efficiency meant that nutrient activity in plant tissue was more at the higher RZT. However, Gavito *et al.*, (2001) found that P shoot utilisation efficiency decreases in wheat with increase in RZT. Hybrid maize (FHY-396) efficiently utilized shoot P while Zn utilisation efficiency of indigenous variety (EV-7004) was significantly ($p < 0.05$) more than maize hybrid (FHY-396).

Fig.12. Nutrient usage index (NUI) of hybrid maize (FHY-396) and indigenous variety (EV-7004) at low and high root-zone temperatures (RZT) (Low and high RZT differed by 4.2°C)

Nutrient usage index was significantly ($p < 0.05$) increased in both the genotypes when grown at the higher RZT (Fig. 12). Shahid hussain, (2011) found that the effect of RZT was more pronounced on NUI than NUE. Shoot NUI of Cu and Zn was increased about 60% at high RZT that at low RZT. At the higher RZT, P and K usage indexes were increased by 98% and 140%, respectively.

Root Zone Temperature with Chilling effect of Boron

Chilling in the root zone during early crop growth is likely to affect root growth, root system establishment and the uptake of boron (and other nutrient) than oil seed crops Ye *et al.*, (2003). Chilling decreases root hydraulic conductance and slows down water absorption on the one hand and on the other hand, impairs stomatal control which leads to excessive water loss and leaf wilting (Capell and Dorffling, 1993; Bloom *et al.*, 2004).

Subtropical / tropical species: (e.g. cucumber, cassava, sunflower), root chilling at 10–17°C decreases B uptake efficiency and B utilization in the shoot and increases the shoot : root ratio,

Chilling-tolerant temperate species: (e.g. oilseed rape, wheat) require much lower root chill temperatures (2–5°C) to achieve the same responses.

Table 8. Effects of chilling root zone temperature on B nutrition in crop species of different chilling sensitivities (* the sensitivity ranking was based on Kratsch and Wise, 2000)

Species	Chilling sensitivity*	Root temp. (°C) (day/night)	Canopy temp. (°C)	B supply (µM B)	Chilling effects on B nutrition	References
Cassava	Extreme	18	Ambient	46	Severe B deficiency symptoms in roots first and then in shoots later. Decreased B absorption rate. Increased shoot : root ratio	Forno <i>et al.</i> , 1979
Sunflower	Intermediate	12	Ambient	0.08, 0.16, 0.25, 0.62, and 6.5	Induced B deficiency symptoms in young leaves at 0.25 µM (but not at 17°C and above), decreased B uptake at all B supply levels, B transport from root to shoot, B partitioning into young leaves. Increased shoot : root ratio	Ye <i>et al.</i> , 2000
Tomato	Intermediate	10	Ambient	93	No B deficiency symptom, decreased B absorption by roots	Tindall <i>et al.</i> , 1990
Wheat	Tolerant	5 (night only)	5 (night only)	0, 10	No B deficiency symptom, decreased B concentrations in the youngest emerging leaf (flag leaf), but increased B concentration in the ear at 10 µM B and decreased at 0 µM B.	Huang <i>et al.</i> , 1996
Oilseed rape	Tolerant	10	Ambient	0.13, 0.19, 8.3	Decreased shoot : root ratio, delayed B deficiency symptoms at 0.13 µM B, increased shoot B partitioning into actively growing leaves without effect on net B uptake rate, and increased B concentration in the youngest fully opened leaves	Ye <i>et al.</i> , 2003
Oilseed rape	Tolerant	2-5	Ambient	0.2, 9.1	Direct transfer from 10-12 to 2-5 °C in root zone for 5 d decreased water use (per plant), increased shoot : root ratio, B uptake rate, B translocation into shoot, and B partitioning into the new leaves, regardless of B supply.	Ye, 2005

The intrinsic chilling sensitivity of crop species seems to be a determining factor in responses of B uptake / transport and B partitioning to root chills (Table 8). However, exposure to 10 °C in the root zone did not decrease B uptake in chilling-tolerant species, such as oilseed rape and wheat (Huang *et al.*, 1996; Ye *et al.*, 2003).

Root Zone Temperatures on the Phytoextraction of Boron and Aluminium with Potato plants

The study conducted at different root zone temperatures on the concentration and content of B and Al in potato plants was examined using four different treatments of plastic mulches: T1: transparent polyethylene; T2: white polyethylene; T3: coextruded black and white polyethylene; T4: black polyethylene. An open-air treatment (T0) was used as control. The results showed significantly positive effects of the plastic covers on the root-zone temperatures: T0=16°C, T1=20°C, T2=23°C, T3=27°C and T4=30°C. The soil temperature was measured at 15 cm in depth, using probes (107 type) from Campbell Scientific TM. Root zone temperature was measured (six measurements at 4-hour intervals) every 3 days of the crop cycle.

The different thermal conditions significantly affected the total B concentrations in roots, because T2 and T3 reached maximum concentrations, with 42% more than T0 for both treatments, while the lowest level was given in T1 (some 13% lower than T0). In tubers, the highest levels in total B were observed in T2 and T3 with 27 and 18% higher than T0, respectively, while T1 and T4 obtained similar concentrations to T0. With respect to the B in the stems (Table 9), the highest concentrations were given in T2 and T3, with an increment of 14% in relation to the control, and the lowest level was given in T1 (20% lower than T0), while T4 did not differ statistically from the

control. Finally, in

leaflets, the highest concentration of total B was given in T3 (13% higher than T0) and T1 as 12% lower than T0, while T2 and T4 obtained practically equal concentrations to the control.

Root Zone Temperatures with Al interaction

Different temperature in the root zone significantly affects the total Al concentration (Mourad Baghour *et al.*, 2002). Strid, (1996) reported synergic effect is observed between RZT and Al concentrations, because the high temperature increases the absorption of Al, showing severe symptoms of Al toxicity at 25⁰C than 15⁰C.

The different temperature in the root zone significantly affected the total Al concentration, evident in the roots of T2, the highest value exceeding control (T0) by 15%, and the lowest concentration being obtained in T4. In the tubers, the highest concentrations were found in T2 and T3, at some 14 and 9%, respectively, higher than control, while T1 was 45% lower than control. For the stems, the highest values were reached in T0 and the lowest in T1 and T3. Finally, in the leaves, T2 and T3 showed the highest concentrations, some 69 and 73% higher than control, while T1 and T0 gave lower values.

Soluble Al in the roots proved higher in T2, surpassing T0 values by 84%, and in T0, we observed the lowest value. In the tubers, T3 showed the highest soluble Al concentration, some 72% higher than in T0, while T1 showed the lowest (17% less than T0). In the stems, T3 and T4 gave the highest levels, surpassing T0 by 17 and 15%, respectively, and the lowest values were obtained in T0 and T1. Finally, in the leaflets, T2 to T4 did not differ statistically, exceeding T0 and T1 concentrations. Mourad Baghour *et al.* (2007) conclude that under our experimental conditions, the potato plant can be a hyper accumulator of B and Al, aided by the control of the root temperature by the mulch application.

Root Zone Temperature Influences Zinc Requirement in Maize

Temperature is an important plant growth factor (Fageria *et al.*, 1997; Pregitzer and King, 2005). Soil temperature affects the rates of physico-chemical and biological processes of nutrient availability in soils and hence affects nutrient uptake and growth of plants. However, influence of soil temperature on nutrient uptake by plant roots has not been thoroughly investigated (Bowen, 1991; Pregitzer and King, 2005).

The zinc (Zn) requirement of a maize (*Zea mays* L.) hybrid ('FHY-396') and an indigenous variety ('EV-7004') was measured at low (22.4 ± 5°C) and high (28.8 ± 5°C) root-

zone temperatures (RZT). Four Zn rates (0, 3, 9 and 27 mg kg⁻¹ soil) were applied to a calcareous loam soil in pots for the glasshouse study.

In both the cultivars, Zn uptake per unit root dry matter ($\mu\text{g Zn plant}^{-1} \text{g}^{-1}$ root dry

matter) was significantly ($P < 0.01$) increased at high RZT than at low RZT (Figure 13). Incremental Zn application rates significantly ($P < 0.01$) increased Zn uptake per unit root dry matter. Increased Zn uptake per unit root dry matter at high RZT could be attributed to temperature depended root and soil physico-chemical and biological processes.

The relationship of relative shoot dry matter with concentration of Zn in shoots of maize hybrid 'FHY-396' and variety 'EV-7004' regardless of the RZT, maximum relative shoot dry matter yield in hybrid 'FHY-396' and variety 'EV-7004' was produced when Zn was applied at 9 and 3 mg Zn kg⁻¹ soil, respectively. Shoot and root dry matter yields were significantly more at the higher RZT. Zinc concentration in roots and shoots of both the cultivars increased with Zn application rates and was significantly higher at the higher RZT. Cultivars differed in optimum shoot Zn concentration and this difference was narrowed down at high RZT. S. Hussain *et al.* (2010) concluded high RZT had a positive effect on growth and Zn nutrition of maize cultivars. Genetic differences among species and cultivars exist for response to soil temperatures.

Likewise, Zn requirement of maize changes with cultivar and RZT. The C_{Zn} C ranged from 25 to 39 mg Zn kg⁻¹ plant tissue for optimum growth of both the cultivars at low and high RZT. Therefore, further studies are warranted on nutritional requirement of crops for their sustained production under changing climatic conditions.

RZT is important for plant growth & development in various stages at different temperature. Optimum RZT helps in physico-chemical and biological processes of plants and nutrient uptake. The nature of RZT increases or decreases the concentration, uptake and nutrient use efficiency. The RZT may have direct adverse effect on plants growth, development and yield under rainfed conditions. Thus ideal RZT would improve seed germination, water / nutrient uptake in plant and maintain physico-chemical properties of soil and plant.

Future thrust

- Identification of RZT in different plants and their optimal temperature for effective crop growth.
- Integration of RZT with nutrients application for attaining ecologically better fertilizer management.
- Better identification of RZT may have the advantage of requiring lower rates of fertilizer or less frequent applications.
- Conducting periodic surveys of the RZT status of crops and soil in different climatic region.

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